

Relationship between Scabies and Quality of Life in Islamic Boarding School X Surabaya

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Abstract

Quality of life is individual's perception of their existence in life. A person's quality of life can be affected by several things, including scabies. This research was conducted to analyze the relationship between scabies and the quality of life of students in one of Islamic boarding school in Surabaya. This research is a cross-sectional study with primary data obtained through scabies examination and quality of life measurement using WHOQOL questionnaire. The result of this study was that there was no relationship between scabies and quality of life ($p=0,057$).

Keywords: Scabies; Quality of Life; Islamic Boarding School; Surabaya

1. Introduction

Quality of life based on the World Health Organization in 2012 is the perception of each individual towards their existence in the context of cultural norms that apply in their environment. A person's quality of life can be influenced by several things, including scabies [1]. Scabies affects the quality of life that can occur in children and adults due to embarrassment, limiting activities, and patients generally feel ostracized by their surroundings [2]

Scabies is a parasitic infection caused by *Sarcoptes Scabiei* var *Hominis* which is a disease that is common in worldwide, but is more common in tropical, hot countries and areas with high population density [3] Scabies has been identified by WHO as one of the 20 Neglected Tropical Disease (NTD) in 2017.

There are 72,500 out of 36,269,500 (0,2%) people in East Java province suffer from scabies [4]. The results of research conducted by Elzatillah (2019) in Delfani (2020) showed that 72.2% of the incidence of scabies attacked Islamic boarding school students or santri [5]. Research conducted by Purwanto in 2016 showed that 41.9% of santri aged 11-16 years suffered from scabies [6].

The impact of having scabies can not only cause severe itchiness that can last for as long to a year, but it can also have an impact on the economic burden of individuals, families, communities, and health systems due to the high cost of the scabies treatment and can be even more expensive if the patient has complications due to secondary infections by the scabies bacteria that cause major scabies [7].

Scabies can also affect the quality of life of its sufferers. Based on research conducted by Purwanto in 2016, scabies has greatly affect on the quality of life of santri with scabies [8]. Research conducted by Savira in 2020 also found that 50% of santri with scabies were greatly affected on their quality of life [9].

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However, that research is not in line with research conducted by Chowdhry in 2020. Chowdhry found that in adult respondents scabies affecting the quality of life mildly was 62.1%, moderately was 25.7%, and did not affect the quality of life was 12.1%, while in children respondents who were mildly affected 44.1% and did not affect the quality of life was 55.9% [1].

The effect of scabies on quality of life can depend on the degree of severity that is experienced by the sufferer. The difference in results obtained through previous studies led to this study being conducted to analyze the relationship between scabies and the quality of life of santri at one of the boarding schools in Surabaya.

2. Material and methods

The type of research used in this study used analytical observational research with a quantitative research approach. The design used in this research is cross-sectional. Variabel dependen dari penelitian ini adalah kualitas hidup. Sedangkan variabel independen adalah skabies. The dependent variable of this study is quality of life. While the independent variable is scabies. The variables used in this study are primary data obtained through the examination of scabies in santri conducted by a doctor at Islamic Boarding School X's clinic and a quality of life obtained using the WHOQOL instrument.

Data analysis was carried out to determine whether there was or there was not a relationship between variables by conducting the Chi-Square test with the help of the SPSS computer application using the cross-tabulation test, which is a 2 x 2 cross tabulation table. Respondents of this study were taken using simple random sampling technique. Of the 855 junior high school students, the sample that must be taken is 145 students.

3. Results

3.1. Characteristics of Respondents

Table 1 Frequency distribution of age

Age	Frequency	Percentage (%)
12	20	13.8
13	74	51.0
14	35	24.1
15	16	11.0
Total	145	100.0

Table 1 shows that it is known that most of santri at Islamic Boarding School X are 13 years old, namely 74 people (51%).

Table 2 Frequency distribution of gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Girls	67	46.2
Boys	78	53.8
Total	145	100.0

Table 2 shows that it is known that most of santri at Islamic Boarding School X are boys, namely 78 people (53.8%).

Univariate analysis results

Table 3 Frequency distribution of scabies

Scabies	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	61	42.1
No	84	57.9
Total	145	100.0

Table 3 shows that most of santri did not suffer scabies, namely 84 people (57.9%).

Table 4 Frequency distribution of quality of life

Quality of Life	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Good	51	35.2
Moderate	70	48.3
Poor	24	16.6
Total	145	100.0

Table 4 shows that most of santri have a moderate quality of life, namely 70 people (48.3%).

3.2. Bivariate analysis**Table 5** Cross-tabulation of the relationship between scabies and quality of life

Scabies	Quality of Life						Total		p-value
	Good		Moderate		Poor				
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	
Yes	17	27.9	29	47.5	15	24.6	61	100.0	0.057
No	34	40.5	41	48.8	9	10.7	84	100.0	
Total	51	35.2	70	48.3	24	16.6	145	100.0	

Table 5 shows that the results of analysis of the relationship between scabies and the quality of life of students obtained 17 students (27.9%) suffered from scabies with good quality of life, 29 students (47.5%) suffered from scabies with moderate quality of life, and 15 students (24.6%) suffered from scabies with poor quality of life. The statistical test results obtained a $p > 0.05$ value, namely 0.057. It can be concluded that there is no relationship between the incidence of scabies and quality of life.

4. Discussion

In this research, students who experienced poor quality of life were mostly experienced by students aged 13 years, namely 12 students (50%). This is related to the adaptation period still being undergone by new students and the age range of these students who still have unstable emotions, causing students to be more likely to experience poor quality of life [10].

Based on table 2, it was found that the results that boys who became respondents were 78 students, namely 53.8% of the total respondents. The results of this study are relevant to previous research conducted at Pesantren Al-Baqiyatusshalihah Tanjung Jabung Barat which found that the characteristics of respondents based on gender were

more respondents with male gender [11]. Male adolescents were found to have higher social loneliness scores than female adolescents, which may make it more difficult for male adolescents to find a supportive environment than female adolescents [12], it can lead to affect the quality of life of male adolescents.

Scabies are associated with embarrassment and visible sores on the skin surface [1]. Night itchininess that disturbs sleep and lesions that can lead to secondary infection by bacteria that may also affect the quality of life of people with scabies [9]. Based on the results of this research, there were 17 students (27.9%) with scabies who had a good quality of life, 29 students (47.5%) who had a moderate quality of life, and 15 students (24.6%) who had a poor quality of life. This research is in line with the research conducted by Febrina in 2020 who found that most students, namely 20 students with scabies (62.5%), are slightly affected by their quality of life, and 8 students with scabies (25.5%) are moderately affected by their quality of life [13].

This study is not in line with research conducted by Purwanto in 2016, that scabies was affecting the quality of life of students with scabies greatly and also research conducted by Savira in 2020 who found that 50% of students with scabies were affected by their quality of life greatly. Some factors that cause differences in research results related to the level of quality of life of a person affected by a particular disease include how long a person has suffered from the disease. This is related to the severity of scabies which is related to quality of life [2].

5. Conclusion

Based on the results conducted in this research, there is no relationship between scabies and quality of life in Islamic Boarding School X. It was found that 61 out of 145 students had scabies and 24 out of 145 students had poor quality of life.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest.

Statement of ethical approval

This research has been approved by the ethics committee of the Faculty of Dentistry with ethical number 299/HRECC.FODM/III/2023.

Statement of informed consent

All respondents have agreed to do this research by signing informed consent.

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